

Automatic Differentiation for Inovesalib

bwRSE4HPC Project Proposal

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Project Partners:	Felipe Donoso Aguirre ³
Scientific field:	Computational Physics
Subfield:	Beam Physics
Start:	2026-04-06
Duration:	3 months
Type of Work:	Refactoring, AD Integration
License:	Open Source
Link:	https://gitlab.kit.edu/felipe.aguirre/inovesalib
Programming Language:	C++, Python
Technologies:	Enzyme AD, pybind11, FFTW
Target Cluster:	HoreKa

1. Project Summary

The project aims to transform the Inovesalib Vlasov-Fokker-Planck solver into a matrix-free, differentiable C++ solver. This refactoring will enable exact gradient computations using reverse-mode automatic differentiation (AD), unlocking new capabilities for gradient-based parameter optimization.

2. Problem Statement

The current Inovesalib architecture offers gradient calculation for the forward and backward evolution but relies on finite differences for numerical differentiation for the parameters, which is computationally expensive. The lack of exact, machine-precision gradient computations prevents users from efficiently performing large-scale physics parameter optimizations or solving complex inverse problems.

3. Suggested Solution

The solver will be refactored using a hybrid Automatic Differentiation approach. Standard mathematical operations (e.g., Fokker-Planck stencils) will be automatically differentiated using the LLVM-based Enzyme AD framework. External library calls, specifically FFTW for wake potentials, will utilize manually implemented adjoints (VJPs) via IFFT. For other complex boundaries, such as cubic interpolations for drift maps, we will initially test Enzyme's auto-differentiation capabilities to benchmark performance before considering custom manual rules.

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4. Milestones

Week 2 setting up CI with tests

Week 4 Refactor to isolate pure operators.

Week 6 Build Enzyme Proof-of-Concept for the Fokker-Planck operator.

Week 10 Combine Enzyme AD with manual adjoint (IFFT) for FFT operations and test Enzyme's performance on interpolation.

Week 12 Finalize testing and documentation.

5. Deliverables

- Refactored C++ library featuring pure functions with hybrid forward and backward (VJP) passes.
- Benchmark comparing Enzyme auto-differentiation versus manual parameter optimization.
- Comprehensive test suite validating AD gradients against finite differences.
- Improved adherence to research software standards.
- Technical documentation, API reference, and optimization tutorials.

6. Expected Contributions

- Active collaboration and feedback
- Access to the Inovesalib source code, simulation test cases and the computing resources used for testing
- Appropriate acknowledgment, up to co-authorship in scientific publications resulting from the refactored capabilities.